

ANALYSIS OF THE DYNAMICS OF QUANTITATIVE INDICATORS OF HIGHER EDUCATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP UNIVERSITY

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Abstract. *In this article, within the framework of scientific understanding, an analysis of statistical data is carried out, reflecting the quantitative indicator of higher educational institutions and students in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Particular attention is paid to the development of an entrepreneurial university as a key factor in modernizing the education system and training qualified specialists for the national economy. The author provides results, the data of which help to identify trends in the development of an entrepreneurial university and factors in increasing the number of students.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurial university, higher education system, management, statistical data, economics, labor market.*

INTRODUCTION

The transformation of the higher education system is associated with a change in the trajectory of the functioning of higher educational institutions, modification of their ideologies, transformation of educational and research activities into innovative processes that correspond to the global market of economic and educational services.

At the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev carried out fundamental and meaningful reforms in the education system, which must meet the requirements of the global educational process. The process of further improving and strengthening legal reforms and transformations in the country is underway [3]. The created legal framework in the field of transformation of the education system is defined as a priority direction for increasing the share of investments in the development of human capital, training a harmoniously developed generation, which represents a fundamental force in the implementation of democratic reforms in the conditions of modernization and stable development of the country's economy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

This study is based on the traditional descriptive method, analytical method, and statistical data analysis method. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was the research of leading scientists who examined various aspects of the development and formation of the entrepreneurial model of universities. Among the scientists we can highlight B. Clark [10], H. Thorpe [12], B. Goldstein [12], I. Gainutdinova [2], S. Shkuratov [9], P. Schulte [11] and others.

In modern conditions, the transition from the classical model to the entrepreneurial one is dynamically developing. New developing structures of modern higher education are being formed.

According to S. Shkuratov, entrepreneurial universities “are distinguished by a high level of commercialization of educational activities and scientific research, and an entrepreneurial style of work” [9].

According to modern management terminology, an “entrepreneurial organization” represents a management mechanism, the internal structure of an organization, and the organization’s position towards other entities.

Note that the entrepreneurial model of the university is based on a number of elements. Among them are the organizational process, initiative, and income level.

The opinion of P. Schulte, where an entrepreneurial university is an educational institution of an innovative format, operating in conditions of risk and dynamic demand, attracts attention in terms of the problems of our research [11].

I. Gainutdinova believes that an entrepreneurial university helps to attract a large amount of financial investments to educational institutions, both from large corporations and from the government, and to generate profits from their own entrepreneurial activities [2].

Based on the point of view of B. Clark, the organizational feature of an entrepreneurial university is associated with innovation, expressed in the reorganization of structural changes, an increase in financial income, an entrepreneurial approach in the market and among business structures [10].

The organizational structure of entrepreneurial universities is associated with the expansion of academic units of the traditional format towards new structural elements in contact with the external environment. There is a process of establishing cooperation and interaction with organizations, business structures, and industry, that is, there is a process of transfer and management of knowledge and entrepreneurial skills [1].

With the help of active interaction with the increased periphery, a new tool for monitoring socio-economic changes is being formed, in which the requirements of society and needs are paramount.

It should be noted that the entrepreneurial university provides educational services, promotes research and development and international projects.

Significant in the field of research is the opinion of H. Thorpe and B. Goldstein, an entrepreneurial university is “a unique educational community with a century-old history, an established corporate culture, which in turn is the driving force of the entrepreneurial spirit of the university” [12].

RESULTS

The development of educational and scientific-innovative activities within the framework of commercial activities of higher educational institutions is an important aspect of modern higher education. This helps create strong links between education and the real needs of business and society, and promotes economic progress and development.

The entrepreneurial university model is an approach that allows universities to develop their activities using the principles of entrepreneurship. In Uzbekistan, as in many other countries, the entrepreneurial model of universities has become popular in recent years. It allows universities to develop their educational, scientific and innovative activities.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, significant efforts have been made to reform the education and science systems. Some of them are reflected in the following documents:

1. Development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 [7]. This document was developed with the aim of ensuring sustainable economic and social development of the country, as well as improving the quality of life of the population. It contains measures to modernize the education and science system, including the creation of new educational institutions, advanced training of teachers, improvement of the material and technical base of schools and universities, as well as expansion of international cooperation in the field of science and technology.

2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further improve the higher education system” [5]. This resolution was adopted in 2017 and contains measures to improve the higher education system in Uzbekistan. It provides for the creation of new universities, improving the quality of education, expanding international cooperation and other measures.

3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further improve state policy in the field of science and public administration in the field of innovative development” [4]. This resolution was adopted in 2021 and contains measures to develop innovation activities in Uzbekistan. It provides for the creation of new innovation centers, improving the quality of scientific research, expanding international cooperation and other measures.

4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” [6]. According to this decree, it is planned to raise the content of higher education to a qualitatively new level, to establish a system for training highly qualified personnel who can find their place in the labor market and make a worthy contribution to the stable development of the social sphere and sectors of the economy. Also ensuring the academic independence of higher educational institutions and the phased implementation of the “University 3.0” concept.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the level of competition between universities increases every year, which leads to an improvement in the quality of education and the development of new teaching methods [8]. This process is associated with a number of factors. First of all, globalization and technology development require universal skills and knowledge from the population. Secondly, increased competition is associated with an increase in the amount of information and rapid changes in technology, which requires flexibility and adaptability. Thirdly, competition in the education system is associated with the need to develop the personal qualities of students and graduates for their successful implementation in life.

It must be emphasized that the number of students at higher educational institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan is constantly increasing [13]. Let's consider this information in terms of regions of Uzbekistan in the period from 2019-2022 academic years (Table 1)¹.

Regions	2019-2020 academic year	2020-2021 academic year	2021- 2022 academic year
Syrdarya region	9089	9597	16764
Navoi region	13636	17015	21710

¹ Table - 1. Number of students in higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Source: prepared based on data from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Khorezm region	16216	22787	28741
Jizzakh region	18000	23391	29955
Namangan region	20109	25989	41829
Surkhandarya region	20131	25628	39909
Tashkent region	20914	28509	42828
Kashkadarya region	22452	27835	44222
Bukhara region	24771	35625	43959
Republic of Karakalpakstan	25442	35487	46585
Andijan region	26036	30895	47651
Fergana region	35819	48415	62332
Samarkand region	41093	54827	70772
Tashkent	147283	185512	271182
Republic of Uzbekistan			
Республика Узбекистан	440991	571512	808439

Table - 1. Number of students in higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The table shows that the number of students in the 2019-2020 academic year in the country was 440,991, and in the 2021-2022 academic year 808,439. During this period, the number of students increased by 367,448 people, which is 83.3%.

Moreover, if we analyze the statistical data by region, the lowest increase in the number of students is observed in the Navoi region 59.2%, and the highest rate in the Namangan region, where the number of students has increased by 108% since the 2019 academic year (Diagram 1)².

Diagram – 1. Percentage change in the number of students in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 2019/2020 to 2021/2022 academic years.

² Diagram – 1. Percentage change in the number of students in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 2019/2020 to 2021/2022 academic years. Source: generated by the author based on research results.

The growing demand for higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is associated with the introduction of government scholarship programs and benefits for students. A system of introducing evening, correspondence and other forms of education is being developed in order to increase the flexibility and accessibility of education.

It is important to note that the increase in demand for education is associated with increased access to higher education, the opening of new higher educational institutions and their branches in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Table 2)³.

Indicators	2019-2020 academic year	2020-2021 academic year	2021- 2022 academic year
Number of higher education institutions	119	127	154
including the number of foreign higher education institutions	16	18	25

Table–2. Quantitative changes in indicators of higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to an analysis of data from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of higher educational institutions increased by 29.4% from the 2019-2020 academic year, including the number of foreign higher educational institutions increased by 56.2%.

In addition, another area of reform is the development of distance and e-learning, which allows expanding access to quality education for a wider population and making learning more flexible and adaptive to the needs of students.

The ongoing national reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan are aimed at improving the higher education system in Uzbekistan and providing high-quality and modern education; they contribute to the development of science, innovation and increasing the country’s human resources potential.

At the same time, according to the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2023 planned expenditures on the social sector will amount to 129,891 billion soums, which corresponds to 50.4% of the total expenditures of the State budget. It is planned to allocate funds in the amount of 58,372 billion soums for the education system, in particular for higher education 10,400 billion soums, and for the development of science 1,843 billion soums, which is almost 14% more than was allocated in 2022 [14] .

At the same time, according to the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2023 planned expenditures on the social sector will amount to 129,891 billion soums, which corresponds to 50.4% of the total expenditures of the State budget. It is planned to allocate funds in the amount of 58,372 billion soums for the education system, in particular for

³ Table–2. Quantitative changes in indicators of higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Source: prepared based on data from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

higher education 10,400 billion soums, and for the development of science 1,843 billion soums, which is almost 14% more than was allocated in 2022 [14].

DISCUSSION

After analyzing statistical data and sources, we identified a number of trends in the Republic of Uzbekistan that are associated with the increasing role of higher education in society.

– Economic development and innovation. In Uzbekistan, a trend has been set for improving the economic sphere, knowledge economy and innovation processes. Higher education plays a key role in training specialists with modern knowledge and skills to implement this process.

– Cooperation with international partners. In Uzbekistan, cooperation and interaction with international universities and educational organizations is actively developing in order to exchange experience, develop joint programs and support students and teaching staff.

– Improving the quality of education and providing academic freedom. Uzbekistan has begun a process of improving the quality of educational services provided, including through the introduction of modern teaching methods, stimulating research work and ensuring academic freedom at higher educational institutions.

– Improving educational infrastructure and accessibility to education. An increase in the number of higher educational institutions and the provision of various forms of education contributes to the accessibility of higher education for the general public.

In turn, the increase in student interest in obtaining higher education as part of the development of entrepreneurial universities is due to a number of reasons.

– Increasing birth rates and population lead to increased demand for educational services.

– Uzbekistan actively supports the development of higher education, including the provision of benefits and subsidies.

– The opening of new higher educational institutions and their branches, which correspond to global trends, contribute to the acquisition of higher education, as students strive to meet the requirements of the labor market.

– Entrepreneurial universities are organizations where students receive not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills necessary in the business structure and the global labor market. In our opinion, the development of entrepreneurial skills is a key indicator of the use of modern educational programs in educational institutions. Universities often actively collaborate with the business community, providing students with opportunities for internships, practice, and participation in real-life projects.

– Entrepreneurial universities provide students with the opportunity to access the innovative and technological field, promoting the development of creative thinking and preparation for the rapidly changing demands of the commercialization process. Universities focus on innovation and new technologies, which attracts students who strive to be at the center of the development of new ideas and technological advances.

– Entrepreneurial universities often provide access to mentors and support for strong professional networks, which helps attract students who want to use these connections and resources to achieve their own career goals.

CONCLUSION

Based on all of the above, we can state that in the Republic of Uzbekistan there is a steady increase in the number of students receiving higher education. This reflects the desire of the state and society to develop human capital and increase the level of education and literacy of the

population. This includes improving the quality of teaching, developing practical skills and abilities of students, as well as creating conditions for their further professional growth and development.

Entrepreneurial universities can create their own revenue streams by attracting investment, developing commercial programs and products, and participating in research and innovation projects. This process promotes close interaction with the business community and stimulates the transfer of technologies and innovations, which can ultimately accelerate their commercialization and implementation in the socio-economic sphere of the state.

REFERENCES

1. Асаул А.Н. Организация предпринимательской деятельности. - СПб: Питер, 2005.
2. Гайнутдинова И.М. Модели управления высшей школой в условиях глобализации и международной интеграции: предпринимательский университет / Вестник Военного университета. 2010. № 1 (21). С. 21 – 25.
3. Мирзиёев Ш.М. Мы все вместе построим свободное, демократическое и процветающее государство Узбекистан. Выступление на торжественной церемонии вступления в должность Президента Республики Узбекистан на совместном заседании палат Олий Мажлиса / Ш.М. Мирзиёев. – Ташкент: Ўзбекистон, 2016. - 56 с.
4. Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан от 01.04.2021 г. № ПП-5047 «О мерах по дальнейшему совершенствованию государственной политики в сфере науки и государственного управления в области инновационного развития».
5. Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан от 20.04.2017 г. № ПП-2909 «О мерах по дальнейшему совершенствованию системы высшего образования».
6. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан от 08.10.2019 г. № УП-5847 «Об утверждении Концепции развития системы высшего образования Республики Узбекистан до 2030 года».
7. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан от 28.01.2022 г. № УП-60 «О стратегии развития Нового Узбекистана на 2022-2026 годы».
8. Фатхутдинов Р.А. Управление конкурентоспособностью организации. М.: Market DS, 2008. С. 203.
9. Yuldashev Sanjarbek Arslon o'g'li. (2023). The Solution of Economic Tasks with the Help of Probability Theory. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 26, 26–29. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjet/article/view/4654>
10. Шкуратов С.Е. Развитие университета как предпринимательской организации. [Электронный ресурс] URL: <http://viperson.ru/wind.php?ID=425641>
11. Clark B.R. Creating Entrepreneurial Universities: Organizational Pathways of Transformation. N. Y.: Pergamon Press, 1998.
12. Schulte P. The Entrepreneurial University: a Strategy for Institutional Development / P. Schulte // Higher Education in Europe. - 2004. - Vol. 29. - No 2. - p. 187-193.
13. Thorp H., Goldstein B. The Entrepreneurial University // <http://www.insidehighered.com/views/2010/09/27/thorp>
14. <https://stat.uz/ru> - Официальный сайт Агентства статистики при Президенте Республики Узбекистан

15. <https://api.mf.uz> - Публикация «Бюджет для граждан: утвержденный бюджет на 2023 год» подготовлена в рамках реализации совместного проекта Программы развития ООН (ПРООН) и Министерства экономики и финансов Республики Узбекистан «Финансирование устойчивого развития в Узбекистане».